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MPCD

Zoroastrian Middle Persian
Digital Corpus & Dictionary

MPCD: An API-based Research Environment

mpcorpus.org

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OUTLINE

- MPCD: Project's technical goals
- First things first: Show me your data
- Creating an API-based infrastructure
- Frontend
- Q&A

MPCD: Project's technical goals I

- Create a software platform for creating and manipulating textual and lexical data for Middle-Persian:
 - A collaborative editor for annotating texts and link tokens with lemmata
 - With support for Universal Dependencies
 - With image support for manuscripts
 - UI for searching and displaying data
- Planned technical support for 9 years. Core development: 3 years.

MPCD: Project's technical goals II

- Which technology shall we use?
 - Programming language?
 - Database paradigm?
 - Software frameworks?
 - ...

First things first: Show me your data I

54	#TRANSLATION:	<u>Und nichts wählt. wer nicht die Seele wählt. von nun an fürderhin.</u>				
55	#COMMENT:	This appears together with 1.28 after 1.1 in K43 (quasi 1.3).				
56	ud	W-	mack1993_ch1_sec29	ud	and	CCONJ
57	nē	L'		nē	not	PART PartType=Neg
58	tis	/MND07'M		tis	thing	NOUN Animacy=Inan
59	gīrēd	'HD07WNyt		griftan	pick	VERB Person=3 Number=Sing Tense=Pres Mood=Ind VerbForm=Fir
60	kē	MNV		kē	who	SCONJ PronType=Rel
61	nē	L'		nē	not	PART PartType=Neg
62	ruwān	lwb'n'		ruwān	soul	NOUN Animacy=Anim
63	gīrēd	'HD07WNyt		griftan	pick	VERB Person=3 Number=Sing Tense=Pres Mood=Ind VerbForm=Fir
64	az	MN		az	from	ADP AdpType=Prep
65	-iz	-c		-iz	also	ADV
66	nūn	K'N		nūn	now	ADV AdvType=Tim
67	frāz	pr'c		frāz	forth	ADV AdvType=Loc
68						

First things first: Show me your data II

```
tok = element tok {
  attribute tokId {xsd:int},
  language?, # optional, default: pal
  element UDI {xsd:int}, # UD: ID
  element transcription {xsd:string}, # UD: FORM
  element transliteration {xsd:string},
  element lemma {xsd:string}, # UD: LEMMA
  annotations?, # UD: morphology and syntax
  element tokenSemantics {
    # the meaning as string is stored in dictionary.entry.hierarchizedMeaning.semantics; therefore, we do not need: element meaning {xsd:string},
    element dictRef {xsd:string}?, # (optional) pointer to dictionary.entry.hierarchizedMeaning.semantics
    # semantic domain as a pointer to a concept in the taxonomy is stored in dictionary.entry.hierarchizedMeaning.semantics; therefore, we do not need: element semanticDomain {xsd:string}
  },
  element avestan {xsd:string}?, # corresponding Avestan lexeme if the text is a Zand text and the token corresponds to an Av. lexeme
  newPart*, # if the token located at the beginning of a new text part
  gloss?, # optional "container" for glossings
  element tokenComment? { # free text "container"
    text?,
    uncertain*,
    newSuggestion*,
    toDiscuss*
  }
}
```

Creating an API-based infrastructure I

- APIs allow us to detach data, its processing and visualization from the very beginning
- API implementation means (almost) data reusability

Creating an API-based infrastructure II

- What open-source software frameworks could be used?
 - Flask
 - **Django (PostgreSQL + elastic)**
 - Fast-API
- Which API paradigm could we implement?
 - REST
 - **GraphQL**

Creating an API-based infrastructure III

Why do we use ReactJS and Relay?

- React:
 - Modularity
 - Maintainability
 - Community
 - Easy to get started
- Relay:
 - Relay Store
 - Fragments

Frontend - TextView

Mādīgān ī Gizistag Abālīsī

1. pad nām ī yazadān ī kirbakkarān
2. ēdōn gōwēnd kū gizistag abālīsī ī zandīg az staxr būd
3. mard ī weh ruwān_dōst būd
4. ud rōz -ēw gursag tišnag ō ātaxs_gāh ī pušt mad kū wāz girom
5. ānōh , kas nē būd kē wāz dād hē
6. ud bērōn bē mad
7. ud mard -ēw kē xēsm pad tan mehmān būd padīrag mad
8. u -s guft
9. kū cē abāyēd ēn warzidan ud pad ān ī mardōm nēkih kāmag būdan kē mard -ēw ī čiyōn tō frāz rasēd u -s wāz -ēw nē dahēnd ud sust ud xwār ud anāzarm dārēnd

Andarz ī Ōšnar ī dānāg

1. pursid hašāgird ōšnar ī dānāg kū ēk tā hazār harw mārīg ēd rāy sān -ē pad frahang be gōw
2. ōšnar guft fradom hunar pad mardōmān xrad weh
3. ud ēk pad kardan be harw kār kē pašēmān nē bawēd kirbag
4. ēk pad kardan harw kār mādagwarīhā_dom tis tuxšāgīh
5. ud ēk pad , mardōmān farroxihādōm tis dānišn ud dahišn
6. ud ēk tis ī anāgīh kē az harw anāgīh -ē dušxwārdōm nihuftan nē šāyēd driyōšīh
7. ēk tis az -iš būdan nē šāyēd kunišn ī xwēš
8. ud ēk abāg harw tis gumēxt ēstēd frasāwandīh
9. ud ēk az harw tēzīh -ē tēzdom kāmag ī xēsm

Frontend - TokenView

The screenshot shows the MPCD website's TokenView interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links: Home, Methodology, Technology, Team, Publications, Resources, Texts, Sections, Dictionary, Contact/Site notice, EN/DE, and Logout. Below the navigation is a dark blue bar with the text "Clear Focus".

The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column contains two sections: "Mādīgān ī Gizistag Abālīš" and "Andarz ī Ōšnar ī dānāg".

The right column is titled "Details" and contains an "EDIT TOKEN" section. It displays the following information:

- number: 25
- language: pal
- transcription: gursag
- transliteration: gwl(s)k

Below the "EDIT TOKEN" section, there are two sections: "Lemmas" and "Meanings".

The "Lemmas" section shows two entries:

- gursag (pal) with a checkmark and a plus sign
- hungry (eng) with a checkmark and a plus sign

The "Meanings" section is currently empty.

Below the "Lemmas" and "Meanings" sections, there is a "Comments" section. It contains a table with the following data:

Date	User	Text	uncertain
8/10/2022	parser	Translit: either s written with one prong alone or k is missing	Transliteration

At the bottom of the "Comments" section, there is a plus sign icon.

Frontend - DictView

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aba

<input type="checkbox"/>	Lemmas	Language	Tokens: Token Meaning	Lemma Meanings	Related Lemmas
<input type="checkbox"/>	abar	pal	<ul style="list-style-type: none">abar onabar overabar atabar overabar over	+ at on over	abar xāstan abar xāstan az
<input type="checkbox"/>	abar xāstan	pal	<ul style="list-style-type: none">abar overxēzēd rise	+ get up	abar xāstan
<input type="checkbox"/>	abar xāstan az	pal	<ul style="list-style-type: none">az fromabar overxēzēd rise	+ get out of	abar az xāstan
<input type="checkbox"/>	abarīg	pal	<ul style="list-style-type: none">abarīg other	+ other	+
<input type="checkbox"/>	azabar	pal	<ul style="list-style-type: none">azabar aboveazabar aboveazabar above	+ above	+

Frontend - SectionView

[Home](#) [Methodology](#) [Technology](#) [Team](#) [Publications](#) [Resources](#) [Texts](#) [Sections](#) [Dictionary](#) [Contact/Site notice](#) [EN/DE](#) [Logout](#)

<p>Text Selection</p> <p>Andarz ī Ōšnar ī dānāg</p> <p>Mādīgān ī Gizistag Abālišī</p>	<p>dhab_ch1</p> <p>dhab_ch1_sec1</p> <p>dhab_ch1_sec2</p> <p>dhab_ch1_sec3</p> <p>dhab_ch1_sec4</p> <p>dhab_ch1_sec5</p> <p>dhab_ch1_sec6</p> <p>dhab_ch1_sec7</p> <p>dhab_ch1_sec8</p> <p>dhab_ch1_sec9</p> <p>dhab_ch1_sec10</p> <p>dhab_ch1_sec11</p> <p>dhab_ch1_sec12</p> <p>dhab_ch1_sec13</p> <p>dhab_ch2</p> <p>dhab_ch3</p> <p>dhab_ch4</p> <p>dhab_ch5</p> <p>dhab_ch6</p> <p>dhab_ch7</p> <p>dhab_ch8</p> <p>dhab_ch9</p> <p>dhab_ch10</p> <p>dhab_ch11</p> <p>dhab_ch12</p> <p>dhab_ch13</p> <p>dhab_ch14</p> <p>dhab_ch15</p>	<p>pursid hašāgird ōšnar ī dānāg kū ēk tā hazār</p> <p>harw mārīg ēd rāy sān -ē pad frahang be gōw ōšnar</p> <p>guft fradom hunar pad mardōmān xrad weh ud ēk pad kardan</p> <p>be harw kār kē pašēmān nē bawēd kirbag ēk pad kardan</p> <p>harw kār mādagwarīhā dom tis tuxšāgīh ud ēk pad ,</p> <p>mardōmān farroxihādōm tis dānišn ud dahišn ud ēk tis</p> <p>ī anāgīh kē az harw anāgīh -ē dušxwārdōm nihuftan nē</p> <p>šāyēd driyōšīh ēk tis az -iš būdan nē šāyēd</p> <p>kunišn ī xwēš ud ēk abāg harw tis gumēxt ēstēd</p> <p>frasāwandīh ud ēk az harw tēzīh -ē tēzdom kāmag ī xēšm</p> <p>ēk tis ī az harw tāriḡīh tāriḡdar dušāgāhīh</p> <p>ud ēk band -ē ī az band -ē saxttar waran ud ēk āsānīg -ē az harw</p> <p>āsānīh -ē āsāndōm hunsandīh ud ēk rāh ī ō wahišt</p> <p>šudan drōyišn ī rāst kunišn ī nēk dō payrāyag pad mardōmān</p> <p>ēn weh dahišn dānišn dō hēnd kē xwēštan tar nē</p> <p>kunēnd ēk kē _ društ āwāzihā saxwan ō āsān nē gōwēd</p> <p>ud dudīgar kē az wattarān tis nē xwāhēd dō hēnd kē</p> <p>hamwār zahr pad dil abgand ēstēd ēk driyōš kē harw</p> <p>tis pad niyāz xwāhēd , dō hēnd kē , ud dudīgar pādixšā</p> <p>ī tund nāzuk . dō hēnd tis qarānmīadar dārišn ēk</p>	<p>Andarz ī Ōšnar ī dānāg</p> <p>Section Types</p> <p>section <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>chapter <input type="checkbox"/></p>
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Frontend - What we have learned

- Relay has a steep learning curve:
 - Scarce documentation
 - Outdated external tutorials

Questions?

Thanks!

mpcorpus.org

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